

Only a subset of all even integers in which every even integer can be expressed as the sum of two primes

Keyang Ding*

Abstract: Only a subset of all even integers can be proved in which every even integer > 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes by comparing the total number of elements in three even integer sets: E_{1+1} , E_{a+b} and E at $n \rightarrow \infty$. The total number of elements in each set is a function of the number of primes n used to construct it.

Introduction: The natural integer numbers are the elements of an infinite set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, n, \dots, \infty\}$. If an integer has only 1 and itself as the factors, it is called a prime number. There exist an infinite number of primes, which form an infinite set $\{2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, \dots\}$. Goldbach found that every even integer > 4 , which is less than an accessible large number, can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes. The question is whether the discovery of Goldbach can hold true for all the even integers, which is known as the Goldbach conjecture [1].

Given an integer N , It is very important to know the total number $\pi(N)$ of primes that are less than N . $\pi(N)$ is called the prime distribution function. After he studied the analytical continuation of Riemann zeta function, Riemann made a hypothesis that all the non-trivial zeros of Riemann zeta function are located on the critical line $\text{Re}(s) = 1/2$ and the distribution of the zeros would be the solution to the prime number theorem [2]. Goldbach conjecture and Riemann hypothesis were listed as the 8th unsolved mathematical problems [3].

Recently a recurrence formula of Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ was obtained [4]

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{-s} - 3^{-s} - 6^{-s}} \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \right] \quad (1)$$

It is identical to the original definition of Riemann zeta function in the complex plane $\text{Re}(s) > 1$. Except a single pole at $s = 1$, it converges in the whole complex plane. But it indicates no zeros on the vertical line $\text{Re}(s) = 1/2$.

To prove Goldbach conjecture efforts were made starting from $a + b$, which means the sum of two odd integers with no more than a and b factors of primes respectively. By gradually decreasing the numbers a and b , it was claimed that $1 + 2$ was proved [1], a step away from the proof of $1 + 1$.

* The correspondence should be addressed to keyangding@gmail.com

A method proposed here is based on comparing the total number of elements in three even integer sets: E_{1+1} , E_{a+b} and E . Each set is constructed from n primes and the total number of elements in it is a function of the number of primes n . When $n \rightarrow \infty$, three sets are infinite but $E_{1+1} \subset E_{a+b} \subset E$, which is equivalent to only a subset of all even integers in which every even integer > 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes.

The set E_{1+1} is composed of those even integers of which every even integer can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes. Let us to start with a finite set P of n odd primes,

$$P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\} \quad (2)$$

with $p_1 = 3$ and $p_{i+j} > p_i$ for any i with $j > 0$. If N is an integer between $p_n < N < p_{n+1}$, $\pi(N)$ is used to denote the total number of primes $< N$, that is

$$\pi(N) = n \quad (3)$$

When $N \rightarrow \infty$, $\pi(N) = n \rightarrow \infty$ and the set P will contain all the odd primes.

A finite set E_{1+1} of even integers can be constructed by adding together two primes p_i and p_j from the finite set P

$$e(i, j) = p_i + p_j$$

$$E_{1+1} = \{e(i, j)\} \quad j \geq i \text{ and } i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

An even integer can appear multiple times if the different pairs of two primes result in a same even integer. If it occurs multiple times, the even integer will be counted for multiple times. The total number of elements in the finite set E_{1+1} is

$$N_{1+1} = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \quad (5)$$

When $n \rightarrow \infty$, the set E_{1+1} will become infinite and contain all the even integers of which every even integer > 4 can be expressed as the sum of two odd primes. Obviously the actual total of the even integers in the set E_{1+1} is less than that is calculated by the equation (5) because of having some even integers counted for multiple times.

The set E_{a+b} consists of all the even integers in which every even integer is the sum of two odd integers with no more than a and b factors of primes, respectively, for finite integers $a, b \geq 1$ and $a + b > 1 + 1$. Using p^a to denote the product of any a primes in the set P

$$p^a = \overbrace{p_i p_j \dots p_z}^a \quad a \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

All the p^a s form a set $\{p^a\}$, which contains a total of n^a different odd integers. Define E_a as a set of all odd integers with no more than a factors of the primes in the set P , the total number of elements in E_a is

$$E_a = \{\{p^1\}, \{p^2\}, \dots, \{p^a\}\} \quad (7)$$

$$N_a = \frac{n(n^a - 1)}{n - 1} \quad (8)$$

A finite set E_{a+b} ($b \geq a$) of even integers can be constructed by adding together one element E_{ai} from the set E_a and the other element E_{bj} from the set E_b

$$e(a+b)_{i,j} = E_{ai} + E_{bj}$$

$$E_{a+b} = \{e(a+b)_{i,j}\} \quad (9)$$

The total number of elements in set E_{a+b} is

$$N_{a+b} = \frac{n(n^a - 1)}{n - 1} \left(\frac{n(n^b - 1)}{n - 1} - \frac{n(n^a - 1)}{2(n - 1)} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad b \geq a \quad (10)$$

When $n \rightarrow \infty$, the set E_{a+b} will contain all the even integers of which every even integer can be expressed as the sum of two odd numbers with no more than a and b factors of primes respectively. The actual total of even integers in the set E_{a+b} is less than that is calculated by the equation (10).

From the equations (5) and (10), it is obvious that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_{1+1}}{N_{a+b}} = 0 \quad a + b > 1 + 1 \quad (11)$$

It is equivalent to $E_{1+1} \subset E_{a+b}$ when $a + b > 1 + 1$ and $n \rightarrow \infty$.

The set E is a set of even integers defined by the equations (12) and (13) constructed by the n primes in the set P

$$e(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i^{k_i} + 1 \quad (12)$$

$$E = \{e(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n)\} \quad k_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k_{imax} \quad (13)$$

where k_{imax} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are large integers. The total number of elements in E is

$$N_E = \prod_{i=1}^n (k_{imax} + 1) \quad (14)$$

If $k_{imax} = k$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) and k is a very large integer, the equations (13) and (14) will become

$$E = \{e(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n)\} \quad k_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (15)$$

$$N_E = (k + 1)^n \quad (16)$$

Every even integer in E occurs only once. When $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $k \rightarrow \infty$, the set E is the whole set of all even integers.

From the equations (5), (10) and (16), it is not difficult to obtain

$$\lim_{\substack{n \rightarrow \infty \\ k \rightarrow \infty}} \frac{N_{1+1}}{N_E} = 0 \quad (17)$$

and

$$\lim_{\substack{n \rightarrow \infty \\ k \rightarrow \infty}} \frac{N_{a+b}}{N_E} = 0 \quad (18)$$

The equations (11), (17) and (18) together are equivalent to

$$E_{1+1} \subset E_{a+b} \subset E \quad (19)$$

When $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $k \rightarrow \infty$, and a and b are finite with $a + b > 1 + 1$.

If the extra repeats of every even integer in the set E_{a+b} are deleted, the resulting even integer set is denoted by E'_{a+b} where each even integer appears only once. Then there has the following equivalence

$$\{2, 4, E'_{a+b}(a \rightarrow \infty, b \rightarrow \infty \& n \rightarrow \infty)\} \equiv E(k \rightarrow \infty \& n \rightarrow \infty) \quad (20)$$

From the equation (19) or (20), it can be concluded that only a subset of all even integers in which every even integer can be expressed as the sum of two primes. There should exist an extremely large number N_0 but still finite so that every even integer $< N_0$ is a sum of two primes and that not every even integer $> N_0$ can be expressed as the sum of two primes.

References:

- [1] J. R. Chen, "On the Representation of a Large Even Integer as the Sum of a Prime and the Product of at Most Two Primes", *Kexue Tongbao*, 17, 385 (1966)
- [2] B. Riemann, "Über die Anzahl der Primzahlen unter einer gegebenen Grösse", *Monatsberichte der Berliner Akademie*, (1859)
- [3] D. Hilbert, "Mathematical Problems", *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*, 8 (10), 437 (1902)
- [4] K. Ding, "A Recurrence Formula of Riemann Zeta Function $\zeta(s)$ ", (non peer reviewed), DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4476915, (2021)